

Fertilizer management – organic sources

Effect of sesbania, rice straw, and pre-incubation on urea hydrolysis in wetland soil

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Interest in using leguminous green manure (LGM) crops has increased in the face of high costs of chemical fertilizers and growing concern for maintaining long-term soil productivity and ecological sustainability. Short-duration LGM crops can be inserted into intensified cropping systems, for incorporation before the main crop. The large amounts of residue from high-yielding cultivars also are being burned or incorporated. LGM crops or crop residues usually are allowed to decompose for different lengths of time before the main crop is sown with N fertilizer application.

The transformation of applied N may be influenced by incorporated LGM crops and crop residues. We studied the effect of incorporating sesbania and rice straw residue, and the length of decomposition, on urea hydrolysis in a wetland soil.

Experimental soil was loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.1, EC 0.16 dS/m, 0.34% organic C, 0.06% N, and CEC 8.3 meq/100 g. Ten-g soil samples were treated with 0.2% sesbania green manure and 0.5% rice straw (dry weight

basis). The soil samples were submerged and incubated at $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 1, 7, and 14 d. After incubation, soil samples were treated with a urea solution at 200 $\mu\text{g N/g}$ soil.

Two samples from each treatment were taken 0, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24 h after urea application and extracted with 2 M KCl containing 5 μg phenylmercuric acetate (PMA)/milliliter. Urea concentrations in the KCl-PMA extract were determined by the diacetyl monoxime method.

Urea hydrolysis proceeded more rapidly in soil treated with rice straw than in soil treated with sesbania. It increased with higher concentrations of amend-

ments and with longer periods of incubation.

Urea hydrolysis was calculated as

$$\ln(a-x) = \ln(a) - Kt$$

where a = initial concentration of urea-N, x = decrease in urea-N concentration up to time t , and K = specific rate constant.

Plots of the logarithm of concentration of urea left unhydrolyzed against time t showed linear relationships, indicating that, irrespective of sesbania and rice straw treatment, urea hydrolysis followed first order kinetics. The average time for half the hydrolysis to occur ($t_{1/2}$) varied from 0.37 to 1.86 d; the reaction coefficient for the soil varied from 0.373 to 1.875/d (see table). ■

Regression equations of $\log(a-x)$ (Y) versus time (X), R^2 , reaction-coefficient (K), and $t_{1/2}$ for soil treated with sesbania and rice straw.

Soil treatment ^a	Regression equation	R^2	K (day ⁻¹)	$t_{1/2}$ (d)
<i>1-d incubation</i>				
LGM (0.2%)	$Y = 2.43 - .024X$	0.955	0.373	1.86
LGM (0.5%)	$Y = 2.37 - .027X$	0.956	0.504	1.38
RS (0.2%)	$Y = 2.25 - .017X$	0.662	0.447	1.55
RS (0.5%)	$Y = 2.32 - .031X$	0.904	0.639	1.09
<i>7-d incubation</i>				
LGM (0.2%)	$Y = 2.35 - .035X$	0.932	0.732	0.95
LGM (0.5%)	$Y = 2.40 - .036X$	0.989	0.746	0.93
RS (0.2%)	$Y = 2.27 - .033X$	0.916	0.777	0.89
RS (0.5%)	$Y = 1.19 - .026X$	0.699	1.131	0.61
<i>14-d incubation</i>				
LGM (0.2%)	$Y = 2.05 - .029X$	0.794	1.009	0.69
LGM (0.5%)	$Y = 1.93 - .027X$	0.622	1.217	0.57
RS (0.2%)	$Y = 1.75 - .025X$	0.536	1.468	0.47
RS (0.5%)	$Y = 1.53 - .019X$	0.565	1.875	0.37

^aLGM = leguminous green manure (sesbania), RS = rice straw.

Multiplication of azolla associated with rice

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Multiplication of azolla is limited by several constraints. We studied producing inoculum in a part of a ricefield for multiplication as an intercrop. On the day rice was transplanted, an area 25 m² of 225-m² plots was fenced with a coconut cord tied with *Aeschynomene*

stems (to make the cord buoyant on the floodwater). The wet season experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design, with four treatments and three replications.

Plot A: Half of 250 g single super-phosphate (SSP), 10 g carbofuran (CF), and 10 g phorate-10-G (Ph) was spread on the fenced area (the additional inputs were kept in the middle of the plot in three open polythene bags).

Plot B: Half of 500 g SSP, 20 g CF, and 20 g Ph were applied the same way as in Plot A.

Plots C and D: control for plots A and B, respectively. The additional SSP was applied at 7-d intervals, the additional CF at 16 d after transplanting when insect infestation on azolla occurred. No insecticide was applied to the rice.

Twenty kg fresh biomass of azolla hybrid (IRRI strain No. 4030) was used as inoculum in plots A and B. Half the azolla present in plots A and B was harvested at 4-d intervals and inoculated to plots C and D.

Azolla biomass production was high, with no remarkable difference between

plots A and B. Although insects and snails in plots C and D reduced production, 78-79.5 kg inocula produced more than 225 kg biomass within 16 d, fully covering the plots for the first incorporation was (see table). The second incorporation was at 30 d, when about 85 kg biomass (64 kg inoculum + about 10 kg leftover mass in plots A and B + residual mass in plots C and D) also produced about 225 kg biomass.

The 25-m² area generated adequate inocula that multiplied rapidly, to fully cover the entire field twice in 30 d. Cost was 650 g SSP, 15 g CF, and 10 g Ph. ■

Biomass production potential of azolla in a ricefield. West Bengal, India, 1990 wet season.

Parameter	Plot	4 d	8 d	12 d	16 d	20 d	24 d	28 d	30 d
Fresh biomass (kg)	A	25.3	16.1	20.5	16.3	20.0	18.2	16.5	9.3
	B	21.0	16.3	20.1	16.1	20.5	18.0	16.5	9.0
	C	-	-	-	^a	-	-	-	^a
	D	-	-	-	^a	-	-	-	^a
SE±		1.6	1.1	2.3	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.0
Insects (no./m ²)	A	x	x	5	12	x	x	x	x
	B	x	x	3	9	x	x	x	x
	C	x	3	4	19	22	5	7	7
	D	x	2	4	22	17	6	12	12
SE±			0.56	0.56	1.13	1.69	0.65	0.85	1.13
Snails (no./m ²)	A	x	x	2	2	2	x	x	9
	B	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	3
	C	6	7	5	9	9	8	10	10
	D	4	x	7	9	9	12	14	13
SE±		0.56	1.13	0.56	1.69	1.69	1.41	1.13	0.94

^aAll biomass incorporated.

Fertilizer management - inorganic sources

Plastic-coated urea (PCU) as a nitrogen source for lowland rice

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We compared the response of rice to N from a new PCU (4.5% plastic coating with 44% N) supplied by IFDC and from prilled urea (PU), urea supergranules (USG), urease-inhibited urea (UIU), neem-coated urea (NCU), and rock phosphate-coated urea (RPCU) Jun-Oct 1987 (southwest monsoon) and the residual effect in Oct-Feb 1987 (northeast monsoon) at CSRC (11° N, 77° E, 30 m altitude).

Soil was sandy clay loam, riverine alluvium deposited over laterite, containing 0.7% organic C, 120-8-68 ppm available NPK, pH 5.1, and EC 0.3 dS/m. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with five N levels (0, 37.5, 75.0, 112.5, 150 kg N/ha) in the main plots and six sources (PU, USG, UIU, NCU, PCU, and RPCU) in the subplots, with 3 replications.

PU and UIU were applied in three equal splits (basal, 20 d after transplanting [DT], and 40 DT); USG was placed at 6 DT; NCU, PCU, SCU, and RPCU were basally incorporated at planting. A uniform basal dose of 26 kg P and 25 kg K/ha was applied. Jaya was the test variety.

In the second season, Jaya was transplanted in the same field without altering the layout. A uniform 45-26-25 kg

NPK/ha was applied as PU, super-phosphate, and muriate of potash (45 kg N/ha is half the recommended N).

Responses to N rate and N sources in the first season were significant (Table 1). A fertilizer testing model (FTM) was fitted to the data on grain yield as

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 N + \gamma_1 N^2 + \delta_2 N_2 + \eta_2 N_2^2 + \dots + \delta_T N_T + \eta_T N_T^2 + \xi$$

$\beta_1 > 0, \gamma_1 < 0$

The FTM tested whether response curves for USG, UIU, NCU, PCU, and RPCU were significantly different from response curves to urea. Regression coefficients $d_i, h_i, i = 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$, estimating parameters δ_i, η_i , and their significant levels (Table 2) represent additional effects due to a particular source over the effects of PU. An *F* test for the additional sum of squares resulting from

Table 2. Fertilizer testing model (FTM) regression coefficients (significance levels and R²).

Source	Regression coefficient ^a
PU	a : 2.61631
	b1 : 0.02124**
Additional effects of USG	C1 : -0.00009**
	d2 : 0.01519**
Additional effects of UIU	h2 : -0.00005
	d3 : 0.00446
Additional effects of NCU	h3 : -0.00004
	d4 : 0.00049
Additional effects of PCU	h4 : -0.00001
	d5 : 0.02555**
Additional effects of RPCU	h5 : -0.00013**
	d6 : 0.00016
	h6 : -0.00001
	R2 : 0.9122**

^a ** = significant at the 0.01 level.

Table 1. Influence on grain yield of level and source of nitrogen. Karamana, Trivandrum, India.

N level (kg N/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)													
	1987 wet season							1987 dry season						
	PU	USG	UIU	NCU	PCU	RPCU	Mean	PU	USG	UIU	NCU	PCU	RPCU	Mean
Control	2.1	2.1	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7
37.5	3.3	3.8	3.7	3.4	4.2	3.1	3.6	3.6	3.4	3.1	3.1	3.5	2.6	3.2
75.0	3.8	4.5	3.8	3.8	4.9	3.9	4.1	3.1	3.5	3.3	3.1	3.9	3.0	3.3
112.5	4.0	5.2	3.9	3.8	5.3	4.1	4.4	3.1	3.6	2.9	3.0	3.9	2.9	3.2
150.0	3.9	4.9	3.8	3.8	4.9	3.9	4.2	2.8	3.6	2.7	2.8	3.8	3.4	3.1
Mean	3.6	4.2	3.6	3.5	4.4	3.5	3.1	3.3	3.0	2.9	3.6	2.9		
<i>For comparing</i>							<i>LSD (0.05)</i>							
N levels (main plot)							0.2							
N sources (subplot)							0.1							
N sources at a fixed N level							0.3							
N levels at a fixed or different level							0.3							